

The reactions of phenols with α,β -unsaturated aromatic acids in presence of polyphosphoric acid : synthetic and mechanistic studies

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The reactions of cinnamic acid with phenol itself, catechol, hydroquinone, pyrogallol and 2-naphthol in presence PPA were studied and that with resorcinol was reinvestigated. With phenol itself and hydroquinone were obtained 3,4-dihydro-4-phenylcoumarin (**1r**) and 6-hydroxy-3,4-dihydro-4-phenylcoumarin (**1s**), respectively, as the sole products. Catechol and pyrogallol, on the other hand, afforded, besides the corresponding 3,4-dihydrocoumarins, viz. 8-hydroxy-3,4-dihydro-4-phenylcoumarin (**1t**) and 7,8-dihydroxy-3,4-dihydro-4-phenylcoumarin (**1u**), as the major products, 5,6-dihydroxy-3-phenylindanone (**5b**) and the chalcone 1-(2',3',4'-trihydroxy)-3-phenylpropan-2-ene-1-one (**3d**), respectively, as minor products. But contrary to earlier observation, resorcinol was found to give 7-hydroxy-3,4-dihydro-4-phenylcoumarin (**1v**) instead of 7-hydroxyflavanone (**4e**). 2-Naphthol, on the other hand, afforded the chalcone derivative 1-[2'-hydroxynaphthyl]-3-phenylpropan-2-ene-1-one (**7**) as the exclusive product. The yields of the major products in the above reactions were 50–67% except that with phenol itself yielding **1r** in 40% yield. The structures of all the products **1r**, **1s**, **1t**, **1u**, **1v**, **3d**, **5b** and **7** were established from their various spectral (IR, ^1H and ^{13}C NMR and mass) data. Evidence for plausible mechanisms of formation of the above products was provided.

The reactions of phenols with α,β -unsaturated aromatic acids in presence of different condensing agents evoked considerable interest both from synthetic and mechanistic points of view during the last few decades. The early work in this area includes the synthesis of a fairly large number of 3,4-dihydro-4-phenylcoumarins by reactions of phenols with cinnamic acids and those of cinnamates or the corresponding nitriles with various condensing agents, viz. AlCl_3 , ZnCl_2 , BCl_3 , H_2SO_4 , HCl or polyphosphoric acid (PPA)^{1–8}. Among the various condensing agents, PPA was found to be most suitable. Subsequent studies^{9–13} on this reaction with different phenols and cinnamic acids and those on various phenyl cinnamates in presence of PPA have yielded, besides several new 3,4-dihydro-4-phenylcoumarins, a few chalcones, flavanones and indanones. In course of these studies it was observed^{9–13} that the course of these reactions and hence the nature of the products obtained was found to depend on various factors, viz. nature of the phenols, positions and the nature of the substituents in the phenyl ring of the cinnamic acid and cinnamates, stoichiometry of the reactants, composition of PPA, temperature, the reaction period, solvent, etc. Thus, Chenault and Dupin⁹ studied the reactions of 2,4-, 3,4- and 3,5-dimethylphenols with 2-, 3- and 4-methoxycinnamic acids in presence of PPA at a temperature close to 50° for 24 h with a view to examining the influence of the methoxy groups at different positions in the phenyl rings of the cinnamic acid. With 2-methoxy-

cinnamic acid, 2,4-, 3,4- and 3,5-dimethylphenols were found to give the 3,4-dihydro-4-phenylcoumarins **1a** (56%), **1d** (17%) and **1h** (20%), respectively. The same reaction of these phenols with 4-methoxycinnamic acid in presence of PPA also afforded the 3,4-dihydro-4-phenylcoumarins **1b** (57%), **1e** (21%) and **1i** (24%), respectively. In the reactions between 3,4- and 3,5-dimethylphenols with 4-methoxycinnamic acid were also obtained traces of 6,7-dimethylcoumarin (**2a**) and 5,7-dimethylcoumarin (**2b**), respectively. These authors, however, observed that the reactions of these phenols with 3-methoxycinnamic acid were not as selective as in the cases with 2- and 4-methoxycinnamic acids. Thus, with 3-methoxycinnamic acid, 2,4-, 3,4- and 3,5-dimethylphenols were found to give 3-(3'-methoxyphenyl)-2'',4''-dimethylpropenoate (24%) and 3,4-dihydrocoumarin **1c** (17%), the chalcone **3a** (32%) and the 3,4-dihydrocoumarins **1f** (21%) and **1g** (10%), the flavanone **4a** (17%) and the 3,4-dihydrocoumarin **1j** (25%), respectively.

Chenault and Dupin¹⁰ also studied the reactions of several arylcinnamates in presence of PPA at 80° for 1.5 h in order to examine the effects of substituents on the aryl ring on the reactivity of such cinnamates. Thus, while they failed to obtain any product with phenyl-, 4-nitrophenyl- and 4-acetylphenylcinnamates, 4-chloro-3,5-dimethylphenyl-, 3,5-dimethylphenyl-, 3,5-dichlorophenyl-, 2,4-dimethylphenyl-, 2-methoxyphenyl-, 3,5-methoxyphenyl-, and 3,4,5-trimethoxyphenylcinnamates were shown to give the 3,4-

dihydrocoumarins **1k** (60%), **1l** (90%), **1m** (40%), **1n**, the indanone **5a** (22%), the flavanone **4b** (24%), and a mixture of 3,4-dihydrocoumarin **1o** and the flavanone **4c**, respectively.

- 1a** : R¹=R³=R⁶=R⁷=H, R²=R⁴=Me, R⁵=OMe
1b : R¹=R³=R⁵=R⁶=H, R²=R⁴=Me, R⁷=OMe
1c : R¹=R³=R⁷=R⁷=H, R²=R⁴=Me, R⁶=OMe
1d : R¹=R⁴=R⁶=R⁷=H, R²=R³=Me, R⁵=OMe
1e : R¹=R⁴=R⁵=R⁶=H, R²=R³=Me, R⁷=OMe
1f : R¹=R⁴=R⁵=R⁷=H, R²=R³=Me, R⁶=OMe
1g : R¹=R²=Me, R³=R⁴=R⁵=R⁷=H, R⁶=OMe
1h : R¹=R³=Me, R²=R⁴=R⁶=R⁷=H, R⁵=OMe
1i : R¹=R³=Me, R²=R⁴=R⁵=R⁶=H, R⁷=OMe
1j : R¹=R³=Me, R²=R⁴=R⁵=R⁷=H, R⁶=OMe
1k : R¹=R¹=Me, R²=Cl, R⁴=R⁵=R⁶=R⁷=H
1l : R¹=R³=Me, R²=R⁴=R⁵=R⁶=R⁷=H
1m : R¹=R³=Cl, R²=R⁴=R⁵=R⁶=R⁷=H
1n : R¹=R³=R⁵=R⁶=R⁷=H, R²=R⁴=Me
1o : R¹=R²=R³=OMe, R⁴=R⁵=R⁶=R⁷=H
1p : R¹=R²=R⁴=R⁵=R⁶=H, R³=OH, R⁷=OMe
1q : R¹=R²=R⁴=R⁵=R⁶=H, R³=R⁷=OMe
1r : R¹=R²=R³=R⁴=R⁵=R⁶=R⁷=H
1s : R¹=R³=R⁴=R⁵=R⁶=R⁷=H, R²=OH
1t : R¹=R²=R³=R⁴=R⁵=R⁶=R⁷=H, R⁷=OH
1u : R¹=R²=R⁵=R⁶=R⁷=H, R³=R⁴=OH
1v : R¹=R²=R⁴=R⁵=R⁶=R⁷=H, R³=OH
1w : R¹=R²=R³=R⁴=R⁵=R⁶=H, R⁷=OMe
1x : R¹=R²=R³=R⁶=H, R⁴=R⁵=OH, R⁷=OMe

- 5a** : R¹=OH, R²=OMe
5b : R¹=R²=OH

Talapatra *et al.*¹² synthesized pinocembrin (**4d**) in 50% yield by condensation of phloroglucinol with cinnamic acid in presence of PPA along with a minor product **6** (14%). They also obtained¹³ 7-hydroxyflavanone (**4e**) in 60% yield by the reaction of resorcinol with cinnamic acid in presence

6

7

of PPA at 50–70° for 2 h. The same reaction when carried out at 85–90° and 100° for 25 min afforded^{6,11} **4e** in 12.7% and 20%, respectively. Similar condensation of resorcinol monomethyl ether with cinnamic acid at 50–70° for 2 h led¹³

- 2a** : R¹=H, R²=R³=Me
2b : R¹=R³=Me, R²=H

- 3a** : R¹=OH, R²=R⁵=H, R³=R⁴=Me, R⁶=OMe
3b : R¹=OH, R²=R⁴=R⁵=R⁶=H, R³=OMe
3c : R¹=OMe, R²=R⁴=R⁵=R⁶=H, R³=OH
3d : R¹=R²=R³=OH, R⁴=R⁵=R⁶=H
3e : R¹=R²=R³=R⁵=OMe, R⁴=R⁶=H

- 4a** : R¹=R¹=Me, R²=H, R⁴=OMe
4b : R¹=R³=OMe, R²=R⁴=H
4c : R¹=R²=R³=OMe, R⁴=H
4d : R¹=R³=OH, R²=R⁴=H
4e : R¹=OH, R²=R³=R⁴=H
4f : R¹=R³=R³=R⁴=H

to an isomeric mixture of the chalcones **3b** (12%) and **3c**. The chalcone **3b** had also been obtained by Reichel and Proksch⁸ by the same reaction in 11% yield. However, when the same reaction was carried out¹³ with resorcinol and 4-methoxycinnamic acid in presence of PPA in xylene at 70° for 1 h, neither the corresponding chalcone nor the flavanone could be isolated, and, instead, the 3,4-dihydrocoumarin **1p** was obtained in 56% yield. The same reaction of 4-methoxycinnamic acid with resorcinol monomethyl ether afforded¹³ the 3,4-dihydrocoumarin **1q** in 44% yield.

The results of the above investigations thus clearly demonstrate that the course of these reactions is highly sensitive to the various factors stated earlier. This has prompted us to

study this reaction with some phenols which have not been used earlier and reinvestigate the reaction with some phenols already reacted with cinnamic acids in presence of PPA and also to carry out further investigations for arriving at a plausible mechanism of formation of the products in each case. The results of these studies are described in this paper.

Results and Discussion

We have studied this reaction with phenol itself, hydroquinone, catechol, pyrogallol and 2-naphthol and reinvestigated that with resorcinol using cinnamic acid in presence of PPA at boiling water-bath temperature (95–100°) for 2 h. Phenyl cinnamate and phenyl 4'-methoxycinnamate were separately treated with pyrogallol in presence of PPA under the above reaction condition as part of our studies on the mechanism of this reaction.

Phenol itself and hydroquinone when separately treated with cinnamic acid in presence of PPA afforded 3,4-dihydro-4-phenylcoumarin (**1r**) and 6-hydroxy-3,4-dihydro-4-phenylcoumarin (**1s**), respectively, as the sole products. Under the same reaction condition catechol and pyrogallol, on the other hand, gave, besides the corresponding 3,4-dihydro-4-phenylcoumarins **1t** and **1u** as the major products, the indanone derivative **5b** and the chalcone **3d**, respectively, as minor products. But contrary to earlier observations^{6,13}, resorcinol under the above reaction condition yielded 7-hydroxy-3,4-dihydro-4-phenylcoumarin (**1v**) as the sole product instead of 7-hydroxyflavanone (**4e**) obtained by Talapatra *et al.*¹³ in the same reaction under slightly different reaction conditions. 2-Naphthol, on the other hand, afforded the chalcone derivative **7** as the exclusive product. The yields of the products in the above reactions are shown in Table 1. Except that for **1r** (40%), the yields of the major products with other phenols were found to vary from 50 to 67%.

Table 1. Yields of products obtained from reactions of different phenols with cinnamic acid in presence of PPA

Phenol	Product(s)	Yield (%)
Phenol	1r	40
Hydroquinone	1s	65
Catechol	1t, 5b	62 (1t), 25 (5b)
Pyrogallol	1u, 3d	67 (1u), 18 (3d)
Resorcinol	1v	64
2-Naphthol	7	50

The structures of **1r**, **1s**, **1t**, **1u**, **1v**, **3d**, **5b** and **7** were firmly established from the following spectral evidence. The presence of an unconjugated δ -lactone function in each of **1r**, **1s**, **1t**, **1u** and **1v** was indicated by strong IR bands at

1740–1750 cm^{-1} [**1r**, **1t** and **1v** : ν_{max} 1740 cm^{-1} ; **1s** and **1u** : ν_{max} 1750 cm^{-1}]. The IR spectra of **3d** and **7**, on the other hand, showed bands at 1640 and 1645 cm^{-1} , respectively, which were attributed to conjugated keto carbonyl functions involved in intramolecular hydrogen bonding with phenolic hydroxyl functions. The chelated phenolic hydroxyl functions in **3d** and **7**, as expected, showed absorptions at ν_{max} 3200 and 3400 cm^{-1} , respectively. The IR spectrum of **5b** exhibited strong band at 1785 cm^{-1} , indicating the presence of a five-membered keto carbonyl function of the indanone moiety.

More compelling evidence for the assigned structures of the above compounds was provided by their ¹H NMR spectral data (Table 2 for compounds **1r-x**). Thus, the presence of a 3,4-dihydro-4-substituted (by phenyl group) coumarin moiety in each of **1r**, **1s**, **1t**, **1u** and **1v** was indicated by the appearance of a one-proton apparent triplet at δ 4.19–4.40 [**1r** : δ 4.35; **1s** : 4.40; **1t** : 4.29; **1u** : 4.38; **1v** : 4.19] and a two-proton doublet of AB quartet at δ 2.96–3.19 [**1r** : δ 3.19; **1s** : 3.03, **1t** : 3.02; **1u** : 3.05; **1v** : 2.96] in the spectrum of each of these compounds, which were attributed to H-4 and H₂-3 of their respective 3,4-dihydrocoumarin moiety. The observed multiplicity of these signals was rationalized by the generation of a chiral centre at C-4 in each of these compounds giving rise to an ABX system. The alternative isomeric flavanone formulations of these compounds having their H-2 and H₂-3 also constituting similar ABX system was ruled out by the fact that H-2 of the flavanone derivatives were reported^{9,10,11,13} to resonate at a much downfield position (at *ca* δ 5.5) compared to H-4 of the 3,4-dihydro-4-phenylcoumarins, although the chemical shifts of H₂-3 of both types of compounds are quite comparable. The chemical shift of the proton at δ 4.19 of **1v** obtained by us in the reaction of resorcinol and cinnamic acid in presence of PPA corresponds to that of H-4 of a 3,4-dihydro-4-phenylcoumarin rather than that of H-2 (δ 5.46) of 7-hydroxyflavanone (**4e**) found by Talapatra *et al.*¹³ in the same reaction at 50–70°. The presence of one phenolic hydroxyl function in each of **1s**, **1t** and **1v** [**1s** : δ 8.3; **1t** : 6.96; **1v** : 6.0], that for two such groups in **1u** (δ 8.07 and 8.15) and none in **1r**, coupled with the chemical shifts and splitting patterns of the aromatic protons of all the above five compounds are also consistent with their assigned structures.

The ¹H NMR spectrum of **5b** showed signals at δ 2.77 (2H, d ABq, J_1 16 Hz and J_2 6.0 Hz) and 4.49 (1H, dd, J_1 6.0 Hz and J_2 3 Hz), which were attributed to H₂-2 and H-3, respectively, of its indanone moiety. The spectrum of the compound also showed signals for two phenolic hydroxyl protons (δ 6.40, 2H, br s), two aromatic protons at δ 6.63

Table 2. ¹H NMR spectral data* of **1r**, **1s**, **1t**, **1u**, **1v**, **1w** and **1x**

Protons	δ ppm (multiplicity, J in Hz)						
	1r	1s	1t	1u	1v	1w	1x
H ₂ -3	3.19 (d, ABq, J_1 15.0, J_2 6.2)	3.03 (d, ABq, J_1 15.0, J_2 6.0)	3.02 (d, ABq, J_1 15.0, J_2 6.0)	3.05 (d, ABq, J_1 15.0, J_2 6.0)	2.96 (d, ABq, J_1 15.0, J_2 6.0)	2.97 (d, ABq, J_1 15.0, J_2 6.0)	3.0 (d, ABq, J_1 16.0, J_2 6.2)
H-4	4.35 (app. t, J 6.2)	4.40 (app. t, J 6.0)	4.29 (app. t, J 6.0)	4.38 (app. t, J 6.0)	4.19 (app. t, J 6.0)	4.29 (app. t, J 6.5)	4.40 (app. t, J 6.2)
Aromatic protons (H-5 – H-8, H-2'–H-6')	7.07–7.38 (complex multiplet) [H-5 – H-8, H-2'–H-6']	6.49 (d, J 2.4) [H-5] 6.78 (dd, J_1 8.7, J_2 2.4) [H-7] 6.94 (d, J 8.7) [H-8] 7.25–7.30 (m) [H-2'–H-6']	6.97 (dd, J_1 8.5, J_2 2.5) [H-5] 7.16 (app. t) [H-6] 6.44 (dd, J_1 8.0, J_2 2.4) [H-7] 7.29–7.35 (m) [H-2'–H-6']	6.61 (d, J 8.1) [H-5] 8.1 [H-6] 7.23–7.28 (m) [H-2'–H-6']	7.73 (d, J 9.0) [H-5] 9.0 [H-6] 6.36 (d, J 2.5) [H-8] 7.23–7.28 (m) [H-2'–H-6']	7.08–7.39 (m) [H-5–H-8] 6.75 (d, J 9.0) [H-3', H-5'] 7.04 (d, J 9.0) [H-2', H-6']	6.61 (d, J 8.0) [H-5], 6.36 (d, J 8.0) [H-6] 6.84 (d, J 9.0) [H-3', H-5'] 7.06 (d, J 9.0) [H-2', H-6']
OH	–	8.3 (br s)	6.96 (br s)	8.07 (br s) 8.15 (br s)	6.0 (br s)	–	6.0 (br s) [2×Ar-OH]
OMe	–	–	–	–	–	3.90 (s)	3.92 (s)

*Spectra in CDCl₃.

and 7.11 (each 1H, s) assigned for H-4 and H-7, respectively, and five aromatic protons at δ 7.24 of the phenyl group at C-3.

The ¹H NMR spectrum of **3d** and **7**, on the other hand, showed signals at δ 7.53 and 7.84 (each 1H, d, J 15.6 Hz) and δ 6.61 and 7.83 (each 1H, d, J 15.0 Hz), respectively, which were attributed to H-2 and H-3 of their respective chalcone formulations. The presence of a chelated phenolic hydroxyl proton in each of **3d** and **7** was indicated by the signals at δ 13.4 and 13.0, respectively, in the spectra of the compounds. The two unchelated phenolic hydroxyl protons of **3d** appeared at δ 5.59 and 5.93 (each 1H, br s). The spectrum of **3d** also showed signals for seven aromatic protons. Two of these aromatic protons appeared at δ 6.52 and 7.40 (each d, J 9 Hz), which corresponded to H-5' and H-6', respectively. The five protons of the phenyl group at C-3 of **3d** resonated at δ 7.34 (3H, m) and 7.60 (2H, m). The above protons in **7** similarly appeared at δ 7.35 (3H, m) and 7.53 (2H, m). The spectrum of **7** also showed signals at δ 7.40 (d, J 9 Hz) and 7.23 (dd, J_1 9 Hz and J_2 3 Hz), which

were attributed to H-4' and H-3', respectively, the further splitting of the signal for H-3' presumably being due to long range coupling with the chelated phenolic hydroxyl proton. The four-proton complex multiplet at around δ 7.75 in the spectrum of **7** corresponded to its H-5', H-6', H-7' and H-8'. Thus, the structures of **3d** and **7** are consistent with their above ¹H NMR spectral data.

The structures of **1r**, **1s**, **1t**, **1u**, **1v**, **3d**, **5b** and **7** were also supported by their characteristic mass spectral fragmentations. The mass spectra of **1r**, **1s**, **1t**, **1u**, **1v**, **3d**, **5b** and **7** showed molecular ion peaks at m/z 224, 240, 240, 256, 240, 256, 240 and 274, respectively, confirming their respective molecular formulae. The spectra of **1r**, **1s**, **1t**, **1u** and **1v** were characterized by the appearance of intense peaks at m/z 147 and 146, 163 and 162, 163 and 162, 179 and 178, and 163 and 162, respectively, which corresponded to the ion-fragments **a** and **b**, **c** and **d**, **e** and **f**, **g** and **h**, and **i** and **j**, respectively (Scheme 1). The ion-fragments **a**, **c**, **e**, **g** and **i** were generated by a benzylic cleavage at C-4 of their respective molecular ions. Loss of a H[•] from C-3 of the

Scheme 1. Mass spectral fragmentations of **1r**, **1s**, **1t**, **1u**, **1v**, **3d**, **5b** and **7**.

above ion-fragments gave rise to the ion-fragments **b**, **d**, **f**, **h** and **j** as shown in Scheme 1. The mass spectra of **1r**, **1s**, **1t**, **1u** and **1v** were further characterized by the appearance of intense peaks at m/z 119 and 118, 135 and 134, 135 and 134, 150, 135 and 134, respectively. These peaks corresponded to the ion-fragments **a'** and **b'**, **c'** and **d'**, **e'** and **f'**, **h'**, and **i'** and **j'**, respectively (Scheme 1). While the ion-fragments **a'**, **c'**, **e'** and **i'** were assumed to be formed by the loss of CO from the ion-fragments **a**, **c**, **e** and **i**, respectively, the ion-fragments **b'**, **d'**, **f'**, **h'** and **j'** must have originated by similar loss of CO from the ion-fragments **b**, **d**, **f**, **h** and **j**, respectively. It is interesting to note that the mass spectrum of **1u** is devoid of the peak at m/z 151 corresponding to the ion-fragment **g'**. This is presumably because of the fact that the loss of a H^+ from the ion-fragment **g** (m/z

179) to form the ion-fragment **h** (m/z 178) is much more faster than the loss of CO from **g**. The loss of CO from **h** directly gives rise to the peak at m/z 150 (ion-fragment **h'**) in the mass spectrum of **1u**. An alternative route to the genesis of the ion-fragments **b'**, **d'**, **f'** and **j'** may be the loss of H^+ from the ion-fragments **a'**, **c'**, **e'** and **i'**, respectively. The mass spectrum of the indanone **5b** also showed intense peaks at m/z 163, 162 and 134 which were attributed to the ion-fragments **k**, **l** and **m**, respectively, formed by the loss of a phenyl radical by the benzylic cleavage at C-3 followed by sequential loss of a H^+ and CO (Scheme 1). The mass spectral fragmentations of **3d** and **7** are typical of a chalcone derivative. Thus, cleavage of the C-1 – C-2 bond of **3d** and **7** afforded intense peaks at m/z 153 (ion-fragment **m**) and 171 (ion-fragment **o**), respectively. The same cleavage fol-

lowed by uptake of a H⁺ generated the moderately intense peak at *m/z* 104 (ion-fragment **n**) in the mass spectra of both **3d** and **7**. The mass spectrum of **7** is similarly characterized by the appearance of intense peaks at *m/z* 170 (ion-fragment **p**) and 142 (ion-fragment **q**), which were assumed to be formed by sequential loss of a H⁺ and a molecule of CO from the ion-fragment **o** (*m/z* 171) (Scheme 1).

The structures of the above compounds were finally confirmed by their ¹³C NMR spectral data (Tables 3 and 4).

The degree of protonation of the carbon atoms of each compound was determined by DEPT experiments and the assignments of the carbon chemical shifts were made by comparison with the δ_c values of structurally similar compounds. Thus, the carbon chemical shifts of **1r** were virtually identical with the reported¹⁴ δ_c values of the compound which were distinctly different from those of the isomeric flavanone **4f**. The most diagnostic ¹³C NMR spectral features of the 3,4-dihydro-4-phenylcoumarin and the isomeric flavanone

Table 3. ¹³C NMR spectral data of **1r**, **1s**, **1t**, **1u**, **1v**, **4f** and **5b**

Chemical shifts in δ ppm								
C	1r *	1s **	1t **	1u **	1v *	C	4f *	5b *
C-2	167.5	165.9	167.0	167.8	165.5	C-1	–	188.0
C-3	36.9	37.1	37.0	37.9	36.8	C-2	79.5	47.0
C-4	40.6	41.2	41.3	41.2	40.3	C-3	44.5	44.1
C-4a	111.8	111.3	110.9	104.0	104.3	C-3a	–	115.2
C-5	117.0	116.6	119.4	118.8	118.8	C-4	191.6	118.0
C-6	124.5	154.6	125.1	112.0	111.7	C-4a	114.2	–
C-7	127.5	115.3	116.5	144.0	153.9	C-5	129.6	155.9
C-8	129.0	129.5	153.3	142.9	109.8	C-6	121.5	147.7
C-8a	151.6	145.7	146.0	146.7	151.5	C-7	136.0	121.6
C-1'	140.2	141.9	140.9	142.9	140.9	C-7a	–	142.6
C-2'	127.4	128.0	128.1	128.4	126.8	C-8	118.0	–
C-3'	129.1	129.5	129.5	129.7	129.1	C-8a	150.2	–
C-4'	128.7	127.9	127.9	128.1	127.5	C-1'	138.6	142.5
C-5'	129.1	129.5	129.5	129.7	129.1	C-2'	126.0	127.6
C-6'	127.4	128.0	128.1	128.4	126.8	C-3'	128.7	129.0
						C-4'	128.0	127.2
						C-5'	128.7	129.0
						C-6'	126.0	127.6

*Spectra were run in CDCl₃ and chemical shifts measured with $\delta_{TMS} = \delta_{CDCl_3} + 76.9$ ppm.

**Spectra were run in *d*₆-acetone and chemical shifts measured with $\delta_{TMS} = \delta_{(d_6\text{-acetone})} + 29.6$ ppm.

Table 4. ¹³C NMR spectral data of **3d**, **3e** and **7**

Chemical shifts in δ ppm				Chemical shifts in δ ppm			
C	3d	7	3e	C	3d	7	3e
C-1	193.3	192.0	192.6	C-8'	–	123.3	–
C-2	119.0	117.1	117.3	C-9'	–	134.1 ^a	–
C-3	144.8	147.1	147.1	C-10'	–	134.7 ^a	–
C-1'	116.2	116.0	108.4	C-1''	135.1	134.7 ^a	135.0
C-2'	154.2	153.5	159.9	C-2''	128.0	128.2	128.1
C-3'	136.1	109.5	96.3	C-3''	128.8	128.7	128.6
C-4'	157.1	117.1	162.4	C-4''	129.9	130.5	130.0
C-5'	108.1	129.6	135.1	C-5''	128.8	128.7	128.6
C-6'	127.3	126.2	154.7	C-6''	128.0	128.2	128.1
C-7'	–	127.5	–				

Spectra were run in CDCl₃ and chemical shifts measured with $\delta_{TMS} = \delta_{CDCl_3} + 76.9$ ppm.

^aValues are interchangeable.

derivatives are the observed differences in the δ_c values of their sp^3 -methine (C-4 of 3,4-dihydro-4-phenylcoumarins and C-2 of the isomeric flavanones) and their sp^3 -methylene carbons (C-3 of both types of compounds) as well as those of their carbonyl carbons. Thus, while the carbonyl carbons of the 3,4-dihydro-4-phenylcoumarins appeared at *ca* δ_c 167.0 (**1r** : δ_c 167.5; **1s** : 165.9; **1t** : 167.0; **1u** : 167.8; **1v** : 166.5), the corresponding carbonyl carbons of the isomeric flavanone derivatives resonated at *ca* δ_c 191–192 (**4f** : δ_c 191.6). Again, while the sp^3 -methine carbons (C-4) of the 3,4-dihydro-4-phenylcoumarins appeared at *ca* δ_c 40–41 (**1r** : δ_c 40.6; **1s** : 41.2; **1t** : 41.3; **1u** : 41.2; **1v** : 40.3), the corresponding sp^3 -methine carbons (C-2) of the

isomeric flavanone derivatives resonated at a much lower field at *ca* δ_c 79.0 (**4f** : δ_c 79.5). The sp^3 -methylene carbons (C-3) of 3,4-dihydro-4-phenylcoumarins **1r**, **1s**, **1t**, **1u** and **1v** (**1r** : δ_c 36.9; **1s** : 37.1; **1t** : 37.0; **1u** : 37.9; **1v** : 36.8) also showed downfield shifts of *ca* 7.5 ppm compared with those of the C-3 of the isomeric flavanone derivatives (**4f** : δ_c 44.5). The chemical shifts of the aromatic carbons of the above 3,4-dihydro-4-phenylcoumarins are also in conformity with the proposed structures of the compounds.

The structure of the indanone derivative **5b** was also confirmed by its ^{13}C NMR spectral data (Table 3). Thus, the carbonyl carbon of **5b** appeared at δ_c 188.0 and the sp^3 methine (C-3) and methylene (C-2) carbons of the compound

Scheme 2. Plausible mechanisms of the reactions of phenols and cinnamic acids and those of aryl cinnamates in presence of PPA proposed by Chenault and Dupin^{9,10}.

resonated at δ_c 44.1 and 47.0, respectively. The aromatic carbons of **5b** resonated at the expected positions.

The structures of the chalcone derivatives **3d** and **7** were also further confirmed by their ^{13}C NMR spectral data (Table 4). The virtually identical δ_c values of C-1, C-2 and C-3 of **3d** and **7** with those of the corresponding carbon atoms of the chalcone derivative **3e**¹⁵ [**3d** : δ_c 193.3 (C-1), 119.0 (C-2), 144.8 (C-3); **7** : δ_c 192.0 (C-1), 117.1 (C-2), 147.1 (C-3); **3e** : δ_c 192.6 (C-1), 117.3 (C-2); 147.1 (C-3)] firmly established the chalcone formulations of **3d** and **7**. The δ_c values of the aromatic carbons of **3d** and **7** are also in conformity with their proposed structures.

Although considerable synthetic work has been carried out on the reactions of phenols with α,β -unsaturated aromatic acids in presence of PPA, the exact mechanisms of these reactions are still obscure. Chenault and Dupin^{9,10} were the first to propose plausible mechanisms for these reactions. These authors assumed the formation of aryl cinnamates as the obligatory intermediates in these reactions, and depending on the nature of the substituents in the phenyl rings of the phenols and the cinnamic acid, PPA was assumed to form coordination complex either with the ester carbonyl (with aryl esters of 2- and 4-methoxycinnamic acids) or with the phenoxy oxygen atom (with the aryl esters of 3-methoxycinnamic acid) of the cinnamates (Scheme 2). In the former case an intramolecular Friedel-Crafts cyclization followed by hydrolysis would give 3,4-dihydro-4-phenylcoumarins, while in the latter case heterolytic cleavage of the cinnamates would form acylium ions, which, by an intermolecular Fries rearrangement followed by hydrolysis, would give the chalcone derivatives (Scheme 2). Cy-

clization of the chalcone derivatives would finally give the corresponding flavanones. The formation of an indanone derivative was also assumed to involve similar Fries rearrangement at the position *para* to the phenoxy oxygen atom followed by cyclization.

If the reaction with aryl esters of 2- and 4-methoxycinnamic acids proceeds exclusively through intramolecular Friedel-Crafts cyclization, it should not give any cross-over products when the reaction is carried out with a phenylcinnamate in presence of another phenol. With a view to verifying this contention we have carried out the reaction with (i) phenylcinnamate and (ii) phenyl 4'-methoxycinnamate, both in presence of pyrogallol under the reaction condition used by us. In each case, the products were found to be a mixture of 3,4-dihydro-4-phenylcoumarins obtained from phenol and pyrogallol separately. Thus, with phenyl cinnamate and pyrogallol the products were found to be 3,4-dihydro-4-phenylcoumarins **1r** and **1u** along with traces of **3d** (Scheme 3). Similarly, the reaction of phenyl 4'-methoxycinnamate with pyrogallol afforded 3,4-dihydro-4'-methoxyphenylcoumarins **1w** and **1x** (Scheme 3). The structures of **1w** and **1x** were established mainly from their ^1H NMR spectral data (Table 2). It is interesting to note that in both the reactions no flavanone derivative was obtained. The above observations clearly indicate that the reactions of aryl esters of cinnamic acids proceed mostly, if not exclusively, through an intermolecular mechanism involving the cleavage of the aryl cinnamates to the acylium ions and the phenols. The acylium ions appear to be the obligatory intermediates. A Michael type 1,4-addition of the phenols to the acylium ions followed by cyclization finally gives the 3,4-dihydro-4-phenylcoumarins (Scheme 4).

Scheme 3. Formation of **1r**, **1u**, **1w** and **1x** in the reactions of phenylcinnamate and phenyl 4'-methoxycinnamate separately with pyrogallol in presence of PPA.

The formation of the flavanones may be assumed to proceed through a Michael type 1,2-addition of the phenols to the acylium ions to give the chalcones which on cyclization finally give the flavanones (Scheme 4). The indanones may also be assumed to be formed through a 1,2-addition of the appropriate phenols to the acylium ions, the attack of the phenols taking place through a site of the phenols different from that giving the chalcones or flavanones. Such Michael type additions of phenols to the intermediate acylium ions

are reminiscent of the additions of Grignard reagents to α,β -unsaturated carbonyl compounds. The formation of the chalcones or flavanones would be favored with bulkier phenols which are unable to react in the 1,4-mode due to steric interaction with the phenyl groups of the acylium ions, while phenols of lower bulk would favor the formation of 3,4-dihydro-4-phenylcoumarins involving addition mostly through 1,4-mode. The additions of phenols of intermediate bulk seem to be nonregioselective forming mixture of

Scheme 4 (contd.)

Scheme 4. Proposed plausible mechanisms of the reactions of phenol, catechol, hydroquinone, pyrogallol, 2-naphthol and other phenols with cinnamic acids and those of different arylcinnamates in presence of PPA.

both 3,4-dihydro-4-phenylcoumarins and chalcones or flavanones, the ratio of the products being again dependent on the bulk of the phenols and temperature of the reaction. This was corroborated by the fact that 2-naphthol gave exclusively the chalcone derivative 7. Pyrogallol gave the 3,4-

dihydrocoumarin **1u** as the major product, while the chalcone derivative was obtained as a minor product. The reaction of resorcinol with cinnamic acid at 50–70° gave the flavanone¹³ as the sole product, while the same reaction at 95–100° afforded exclusively the 3,4-dihydrocoumarin **1v**. Similarly,

the reactions of 3,4, 3,5- and 2,4-dimethylphenols with 3-methoxycinnamic acid afforded⁹ mixtures of 3,4-dihydrocoumarins and chalcones or flavanones and cinnamate (only in case of 2,4-dimethylphenol) as stated earlier, formed by both 1,4- and 1,2-additions of the phenols to the corresponding acylium ions. The fact that the reaction of 2,4-, 3,4- and 3,5-dimethylphenols with 2- and 4-methoxycinnamic acids afforded exclusively the 3,4-dihydro-4-phenylcoumarins and no chalcones or flavanones, may be rationalized by assuming the participation of the more stable resonating forms x' and y' rather than the less stable forms x and y , respectively, of the 2- and 4-methoxycinnamyl ions, which can only form the 3,4-dihydrocoumarin derivatives as shown in Scheme 4. The elimination of the anisyl group from the 3,4-dihydrocoumarin **1i** involving coordination of PPA with the oxygen of the 4'-methoxyl group as proposed by Chenault and Dupin⁹ appears to take place by protonation at C-1' of **1i** as shown in Scheme 4. Under the reaction conditions (95–100°) used by us, formation of phenyl cinnamates may not necessarily be an obligatory step in the reactions of phenol, hydroquinone, catechol, resorcinol, pyrogallol and 2-naphthol with cinnamic acid in presence of PPA. Cinnamic acid at the above high temperature may directly be converted to the corresponding acylium ion which may undergo either a Michael type 1,4- or 1,2-addition with the above phenols depending upon their nature to give different products as shown in Scheme 4. The phenyl cinnamates, if at all formed initially, are possibly converted to the acylium ions under the high temperature used.

Experimental

M.p.s. are uncorrected. Silica gel (100–200 mesh) were used for column chromatography and silica gel G for TLC. IR spectra (KBr) were run on a Perkin-Elmer spectrophotometer (Model 782). ¹H NMR spectra (300 MHz) were recorded on a Bruker Supercon FT NMR instrument using TMS as the internal standard and ¹³C NMR spectra (75 MHz) in the same instrument. Mass spectra were recorded with a direct inlet system at 70 eV and the figures in the parentheses attached to each m/z value represent relative intensities of the peaks. All analytical samples were routinely dried over P₂O₅ for 24 h *in vacuo* and were tested for purity by TLC and MS. Anhydrous Na₂SO₄ was used for drying organic solvents. Petrol used had b.p. 60–80°.

General method for the reactions of phenols with cinnamic acid in presence of PPA :

To the freshly prepared polyphosphoric acid [prepared by vigorously stirring a mixture of 12.5 g P₂O₅ and 20 ml orthophosphoric acid ($d = 1.75$ g/ml) at 100° for 2 h] a mixture of the appropriate phenol and cinnamic acid was

added with stirring at room temperature. The reaction mixture was then heated on a boiling water-bath (95–100°) for 2 h. It was then cooled to room temperature, poured into crushed ice and left for 2 h. The liberated solid in each case was extracted with Et₂O, washed with H₂O, dried and the solvent removed. The crude products obtained by the reaction of 1 g each of phenol, hydroquinone, catechol, pyrogallol, resorcinol and 2-naphthol with 1.5, 1.33, 1.33, 1.18, 1.33 and 1.04 g of cinnamic acid, respectively, in presence of polyphosphoric acid (20 ml) in each case under the reaction conditions stated above, were separately chromatographed.

Reaction of phenol with cinnamic acid : The petrol-EtOAc (80 : 1) eluate in the chromatography of the crude reaction product obtained by the reaction of phenol and cinnamic acid afforded **1r** (0.89 g), crystallized from petrol-EtOAc, m.p. 95°; ν_{\max} 1740 (δ -lactone C=O), 1600, 1565, 1490, 1440, 830, 810, 750, 660 and 610 cm⁻¹ (aromatic nucleus); m/z (rel. int.) 224 (M⁺, 100), 147 (45), 146 (70), 119 (40) and 118 (46).

Reaction of hydroquinone with cinnamic acid : Chromatography of the crude reaction product obtained from the reaction of hydroquinone and cinnamic acid gave **1s** (1.42 g) in the petrol-EtOAc (50 : 1), crystallized from the same solvent mixture, m.p. 125° (Found : C, 74.96; H, 4.98. C₁₅H₁₂O₃ requires : C, 75.0; H, 5.04%); ν_{\max} 3450 (OH), 1750 (δ -lactone C=O), 1615, 1580, 1500, 835, 775, 720, 665 and 625 cm⁻¹ (aromatic nucleus); m/z (rel. int.) 240 (M⁺, 46), 163 (62), 162 (100), 135 (32), 134 (48) and 106 (37).

Reaction of catechol and cinnamic acid : The crude reaction products obtained by the reaction of catechol and cinnamic acid in presence of PPA were chromatographed. The petrol-EtOAc (50 : 1) eluate afforded **1t** (1.35 g), crystallized from petrol-EtOAc, m.p. 110° (Found : C, 74.98; H, 4.92. C₁₅H₁₂O₃ requires : C, 75.0; H, 5.04%); ν_{\max} 3420 (OH), 1740 (δ -lactone C=O), 1620, 1590, 1465, 1410, 870, 840, 690 and 625 cm⁻¹ (aromatic nucleus); m/z (rel. int.) 240 (M⁺, 48), 163 (63), 162 (100), 135 (32), 134 (48), 107 (47), 106 (37).

Further elution of the column with petrol-EtOAc (20 : 1) gave **5b** (0.55 g), crystallized from the same solvent mixture, m.p. 122° (Found : C, 74.92; H, 4.95. C₁₅H₁₂O₃ requires : C, 75.0; H, 5.04%); ν_{\max} 3425 (OH), 1785 (5-membered cyclic conjugated C=O), 1635, 1620, 1490, 875, 815, 800, 790, 670 and 640 cm⁻¹ (aromatic nucleus); m/z (rel. int.) 240 (M⁺, 100), 163 (55), 162 (69), 134 (31), 106 (35) and 78 (25).

Reaction of pyrogallol with cinnamic acid : The mix-

ture of products obtained by the reaction of pyrogallol with cinnamic acid in presence of PPA was chromatographed. The petrol-EtOAc (30 : 1) eluate gave **1u** (1.36 g), crystallized from petrol-EtOAc, m.p. 172° (Found : C, 70.29; H, 4.69. C₁₅H₁₂O₄ requires : C, 70.3; H, 4.7%); ν_{\max} 3420 (OH), 1750 (δ -lactone C=O), 1620, 1520, 1480, 890, 775, 730, 620 and 610 cm⁻¹ (aromatic nucleus); m/z (rel. int.) 256 (M⁺, 100), 179 (48), 178 (65), 150 (50), 122 (32), 94 (27) and 66 (20).

Further washing the column with petrol-EtOAc (10 : 1) afforded **3d** (0.37 g), crystallized from petrol-EtOAc, m.p. 152° (Found : C, 70.28; H, 4.68. C₁₅H₁₂O₄ requires : C, 70.3; H, 4.7%); ν_{\max} 3440 (unchelated Ar-OH), 3200 (chelated Ar-OH), 1640 (conjugated chelated C=O), 1610, 1575, 1515, 1435, 860, 790, 770, 745, 680 and 615 cm⁻¹ (aromatic nucleus); m/z (rel. int.) 256 (M⁺, 100), 153 (84), 124 (53), 104 (33), 96 (35) and 68 (24).

Reaction of resorcinol with cinnamic acid : The reaction product obtained by the reaction of resorcinol with cinnamic acid in presence of PPA under the reaction condition stated above was chromatographed. The petrol-EtOAc (50 : 1) eluate gave **1v** (1.40 g), crystallized from petrol-EtOAc, m.p. 125° (Found : C, 74.95; H, 4.94. C₁₅H₁₂O₃ requires : C, 75.0; H, 5.04%); ν_{\max} 3400 (OH), 1740 (δ -lactone C=O), 1610, 1575, 1440, 880, 830, 735, 660 and 620 cm⁻¹ (aromatic nucleus); m/z (rel. int.) 240 (M⁺, 100), 163 (53), 162 (69), 135 (26), 134 (32), 106 (33) and 78 (24).

Reaction of 2-naphthol with cinnamic acid : The residue obtained by the reaction of 2-naphthol with cinnamic acid in presence of PPA was chromatographed. The petrol-EtOAc (50 : 1) eluate afforded **7** (0.95 g), crystallized from the same solvent mixture, m.p. 178° (Found : C, 83.18; H, 5.10. C₁₉H₁₄O₂ requires : C, 83.2; H, 5.15%); ν_{\max} 3340 (chelated Ar-OH), 1645 (conjugated chelated C=O), 1610, 1550, 1520, 1440, 1430, 850, 820, 790, 680 and 625 cm⁻¹ (aromatic nucleus); m/z (rel. int.) 274 (M⁺, 100), 171 (48), 170 (56), 142 (42) and 104 (26).

Preparation of phenyl cinnamate and 4'-methoxyphenyl cinnamate : Phenyl cinnamate and 4'-methoxyphenyl cinnamate were prepared by treating a solution of phenol (0.1 mol) and pyridine (0.1 mol) in dry benzene (100 ml) separately with cinnamoyl chloride (0.1 mol) and 4-methoxycinnamoyl chloride (0.1 mol), respectively, in dry benzene (30 ml). The mixtures were separately heated for 1 h on a boiling water-bath. After filtration and evaporation of the solvent, the cinnamates were obtained in solid state (ca 99%) : phenylcinnamate : δ 6.46 (1H, d, J 15 Hz, H-2), 7.41–7.56 (10H, m, H-2''–H-6'' and H-2'–H-6') and 7.80 (1H,

d, J 15 Hz, H-3); 4'-methoxyphenylcinnamate : δ 3.95 (3H, s, Ar-OMe), 6.88 (2H, d, J 8.7 Hz, H-3' and H-5'), 7.28 (5H, m, H-2''–H-6''), 7.38 (1H, d, J 15 Hz, H-2), 7.55 (2H, d, J 8.7 Hz, H-2' and H-6') and 7.80 (1H, d, J 15 Hz, H-3).

Reaction of phenyl cinnamate with pyrogallol in presence of PPA : A mixture of phenyl cinnamate (1 g), pyrogallol (0.5 g) and PPA (20 ml) was heated on a boiling water-bath for 2 h. The crude reaction products after usual work-up were chromatographed. The petrol-EtOAc (80 : 1) eluate afforded **1r** (0.15 g). Further elution of the column with petrol-EtOAc (30 : 1) gave **1u** (0.47 g).

Reaction of 4'-methoxyphenyl cinnamate with pyrogallol in presence of PPA : A mixture of 4'-methoxyphenyl cinnamate (1 g) and pyrogallol (0.55 g) was treated with PPA (20 ml). The mixture was heated on a boiling water-bath for 2 h. The products after usual work-up were chromatographed. The petrol-EtOAc (50 : 1) eluate gave **1w** (0.2 g), crystallized from the same solvent mixture, m.p. 115°. Further washing the column with petrol-EtOAc (10 : 1) afforded **1x** (0.46 g), crystallized from petrol-EtOAc, m.p. 122°.

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